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NETFLIX BIGDATA ANALYTICS-A STUDY ON IMPROVING CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

Netflix is one of the largest online streaming mediaproviders. It began its operations in 1997. Founded by two tech entrepreneur Reed Hastings and Marc Randolph. The Company's head office is in Los Gatos, California. Netflix's initially started selling DVDs or provide them on a rental basis. Over the period with growth of internet users and the decline of DVD sales and rental services, it changed its business model to video on demand. From 2012 onwards, it started producing its original TV-series and movies. Netflix uses bigdata analytics to understand its customer base better. By using these data, they provide better service or product to the customer. Netflix collects huge amounts of data from a vast variety of subscriber base. It collects data such as the location of a user; content watched by the user, user interests, the data searched by the user, and the time at which user watched. Based on these parameters its algorithm gives a personalized recommendation based on the user interest. Netflix has constantly focused on changing business needs they have moved their business model from DVD rental to video on demand and currently producing original shows. In this paper we analyze various business strategies of Netflix. This paper also analyzes how Netflix with the help of bigdata analytics focused on improving the subscriber's experience and how it helped to be more customer-centric and increased its user base.

Keywords: Netflix, Bigdata, Data analytics, Customer experience, Video on demand, Streaming

1. INTRODUCTION

Netflix, Inc was founded by two tech entrepreneur Reed Hastings and Marc Randolph. It began its operations in the year of 1997. The Company's head office is in Los Gatos, California. Netflix's Main business is subscription-based online streaming services of TV Shows, Originals, Movies, etc. Being the largest media service provider, it has over 148 Million members operated across 190 countries except for China, Iran, North Korea, Crimea, and Syria [1]. During the initial days Netflix suffered huge loss but with the raise of internet users and Netflix changed its business model from traditional DVD rental and sales to the introduction of

online video streaming in 2007. Netflix was able to reduce the loss. To make this possible Netflix needed to change their business strategy. Along with the streaming on movies, TV-Shows from another studios Netflix is also producing its own movies and TV-Shows. From 2010 Netflix started its expansion worldwide starting from Canada in 2010 than in Latin American countries in the year 2011 followed by United Kingdom and other European Countries like Denmark, Netherlands, Norway etc. from 2012 till 2015. In the year 2012 Netflix has split its business of DVD rental service as a Separate division from online streaming division. Till 2017 DVD rental division has around 3.3 million customers and Netflix has plans to keep this service for few more years. The biggest challenge currently faced by Netflix are Maintaining the existing subscribers and increasing the new subscriber count, increase in competition by other streaming providers like Hulu, Disney, Warner Media, Amazon, the rise of the cost to produce the original content. To overcome these challenges Netflix uses Bigdata Analytics. Netflix has heavily invested in research on bigdata analytics it spends over \$1 billion for it. As of today, they have a separate division called Netflix Research that mainly concentrates on data analytics areas such as customer experience, recommendations, machine learning, etc. They are heavily invested in Data Sciences and Data Analytics for their recommendation systems. These recommendation systems understand the users and provide recommendation accordingly.

2. OBJECTIVES

Below are the objectives of study

1. To understand about the evolution of business model at Netflix.
2. To understand about the strategies of Netflix and how new strategies are used to overcome challenges faced by competition.
3. To understand how Bigdata analytics is used by Netflix to improve customer satisfaction.
4. Use of SWOT and PESTLE analysis for recommendation of Netflix future strategies.

3. NETFLIX vs. BLOCKBUSTER: Evolution of Business model

Netflix was the main competitor for Blockbuster Inc which is into the business of DVD sales and rental through their physical stores. Blockbuster started in year 1985 was an undisputed leader in the entertainment service business with more than 2800 physical stores. Blockbuster was selling and renting DVD through its stores across worldwide [2]. Netflix came with the unique idea of DVD sales and rental business without physical store. Using the Netflix website from the catalogue one must choose the movies/TV-shows what they want, and Netflix used to send the DVD through postal service. During the early days Netflix started offering DVD on rental basis. Netflix realized that it is spending more per customer than what it was earning through rent of DVD. So, it changed its business model to Subscription method where it was offering DVD rental to its customers who subscribed for a fixed fee. Unlike its rival Blockbuster Netflix was not charging any late fee from the return of the DVD. Since inception Netflix was not profitable and was losing money one of its founder Reed Hastings in the year 2000 approached Blockbuster CEO John Antioco with the offer of Netflix being taken over by Blockbuster for \$50 Million. His idea was Netflix team would manage Blockbuster's Online brand and Blockbuster needs to

promote Netflix in their stores however this deal was rejected by Blockbuster's team [3]. The major challenge the Netflix faced is a very high demand for new and super hit movies, sometimes this resulted in customer being not happy due to movies not been available. To address this Netflix came up with the idea of Netflix recommendation system this resulted in the decrease of 20% for the demand of new releases compared to the traditional DVD rental services like Blockbuster. Both Blockbuster and Netflix competed against each other for the same market, but their business model was different. Blockbuster business model was based on idea that most movie rentals happen based on the impulse decision of user who may want to watch the movie immediately these are new releases or hit movies, so their stores mainly concentrated on that aspect. Netflix business model was based on considering movies as regular entertainment. Instead of pickup like Blockbuster Netflix delivered the movies through postal service. Customer ability to keep the movies for longer time and convenience to return through postal service attracted more customers to Netflix. Blockbuster was very late to adapt changes and by the time when they realized the threat from Netflix and planned to launch similar model as of Netflix in the year 2004. But due to change in management the idea did not materialize, and they continued their older business model. Finally, the company went bankrupt and closed its operations in 2013.

4. BIGDATA ANALYTICS at NETFLIX:

Netflix was one of the early adapters of Bigdata Analytics in the year 2006 Netflix came up with a challenge that would award \$1 Million to anyone who would improve their existing recommendation system by 10% [4]. The challenge was to develop an algorithm to predict the subscriber movie preference based on the older data. The prize was awarded to BellKor's Pragmatic Chaos team which consisted of Mathematician, data scientist and engineers from different countries [5]. Netflix uses Data Science and Bigdata Analytics in their recommendation systems. In late 1990's, the term recommender system was introduced for the first time in literature of information system [6]. The interest in recommendation system remains as it is widely applicable to solve the practical problems of many companies. Many companies like Amazon, Microsoft etc. have a commercial recommendation system [7-8].

4.1 Netflix Recommendation System: It recommends the subscribers various choices based on their interests. Recommendation systems use Machine learning. It takes inputs from user and recommends appropriately. In Netflix recommendation system collects user data such as the location of a user; content watched by the user, user interests, the data searched by the user, and the time at which user watched. Based on these parameters its algorithm gives a personalized recommendation based on the subscriber's interest. Mostly recommendation systems take user profile as an important parameter. Subscriber profile consists of different types of information such as interest of a subscriber, history of subscriber search query, interaction with system etc. Whenever a new subscriber account is created, or a new profile is added to existing account Netflix will ask the subscriber to choose few genre or titles which can be used as initial parameters for recommendation system. If the subscriber skips this step, then Netflix will populate the user homepage with the popular set of contents. Once the user starts watching the

content then this will super cede any initial preferences provided by subscriber. As the subscriber continues to watch.The content which was watched previously will be used to provide the recommendation further [9-10].

There are two types of recommendation system [11]

1. Content-based
2. Collaborative filtering

Content-based filtering:This type of recommendation system takes the customer information [12]. Suppose a subscriber has watched aComedy movie on Netflix as described in Fig.1. This recommendation system suggests similar action movies to the subscriber.

Collaborative filtering: This kind of recommendation system is based on similar profiles of users [13]. For instance, if a subscriber A watches crime, action, horror movies and subscriber B watches crime, action, comedy movies then subscriber A will like to watch comedy movies and subscriber B will like to watch horror movies. Please refer Fig.1.

Netflix uses Hybrid recommendation system that is the combination of content and collaborative recommendation system.

Fig.1: Recommendation Techniques

5. ANALYSIS:

Both SWOT and PESTLE analysis are performed as per the guidelines mentioned in Company analysis case study [14-20]

Company Background [21]

Company: Netflix

CEO: Reed Hastings

Year founded: 1997

Headquarter: Los Gatos, USA

Number of Employees (2018): 5,500

Public or Private: Public

Ticker Symbol: NFLX

Market Cap (Feb 2019): \$155.81 Billion

Annual Revenue (2018): \$15.79 Billion

Profit |Net income (2018): \$1.21 Billion

Products & Services: Video on demand, online streaming

Competitors: Hulu | Disney+ | HBO| Warner Media | Amazon |

SWOT Analysis:

Strengths:

- Established Brand Name
- Global Customer Base: Netflix is serving over 190 countries worldwide.
- Technology: Netflix is ready to embrace changes rapidly it is one of the early adapters of bigdata analytics and data science.
- Original Content: Netflix is in production of original content and the quality of the content which Netflix produces are liked by many viewers.

Weakness:

- Huge Debt: The production of original content involves huge costs this results in debts.
- Limited Copyrights: For many of shows or movies Netflix has taken rights from other studios. It is becoming difficult to manage the content library as the rights taken from other studios expire and the content will be taken off from Netflix.

Opportunities:

- Expansion into other countries including China.
- Partnership in Europe to meet European laws.
- Alliances: It can partner with various service providers to provide bundle packages at discounted price.
- Potential to earn revenue by other means like advertisements.

Threats:

- Increased Competition: Other Providers like Hulu, HBO, Amazon, Disney and Warner Media are entered or entering the online streaming service.
- Piracy: It is the biggest threat many users download the content by illegal means.
- Increasing the Subscription price lead to subscribers switch to other providers.
- Sharing of Single Subscription between multiple users.

PESTLE Analysis:

Political:

- Due to European regulations Netflix belonged to same category as television distributors. Netflix needs to follow the European rule that 30% of the content needs to be European.
- Due to restrictions of US on some countries like Crimea, North Korea Netflix cannot expand to those countries.
- Due to permission issue by Chinese government Netflix could not expand its business to china.

Economical:

- Change of exchange rates impacts the revenue of Netflix.
- Competitive pricing.

Socio-Cultural

- Many Customers are moving to watch content through their smartphone.
- Netflix is known for charity work like providing scholarships.

Technological:

- Improving quality of streaming with less data consumption to support 4K content efficiently.
- A new software called 'Hermes' is developed by Netflix Research which automatically grades a translation. With the use of this Netflix will be able to serve the faster and good quality translation of shows to different countries.

Legal:

- Due to copyright laws Netflix has introduced blockers that will block the users accessing the contents from other countries this will affect the user base.
- They need to handle the video piracy affectively.

Environmental:

- Netflix needs to work more towards using of renewable energy and reduce the carbon footprint of its data centers.

6. SUGGESTION

Based on the SWOT and PESTLE analysis below are few recommendations

- Netflix to continue its use on Data analytics and Data Science to improve the customer experience.
- It is recommended to reduce the subscription cost as similar as its competitor for developing countries like India.
- Explore other territories for expansion.
- Produce more original content region specific.
- Use of advanced authentication techniques like finger print or facial recognition [22-25] or Multi factor authentication [26-27] for subscriber authentication.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have discussed regarding business model of Netflix comparing it with the business model of Blockbuster Inc and how Netflix was able to beat its competitor to become leading online streaming service provider. We have also discussed about the different kinds of recommendation system and the type of recommendation system used by Netflix. We discussed about the Netflix prize competition and how the winning team algorithm made the existing algorithm of Netflix more accurate. Also, we have analyzed how with Bigdata Analytics is used for its recommendation system to improve the customer experience. Based on the SWOT and PESTLE analysis we have provided few recommendations to Netflix to improve their business strategy.

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